

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object;

Julian Paper Analysis For The Meaning Of The Clouds And Home In The Novel Title "Nanti Kita Cerita Tentang Hari Ini"

Background and Analysis

Abstract: This research paper was conducted with the aim that we know the meaning of the name "Awan". Awan that must always find a way to provide a beautiful atmosphere, protect and comfort the earth and everything in it, a beautiful atmosphere that must provide rain for the earth so as not to dry out and keep the earth from heating due to the heat of the sun. This analysis is also carried out so that we know the meaning of the phrase "Jalan yang jauh, Jangan Lupa Pulang" so that after a long journey in this cruel world, we always have a goal to return to the place where we grew up until we were teenagers.

Conclusion: The language used to write the meaning of the name "Awan" and the meaning of "Pulang" is to use language that does not make it difficult for the reader to feel and think about the meaning of this message. A flash fiction novel with the theme "Nanti Kita Cerita Tentang Hari Ini" written by Marchella F.P. is a very extraordinary ordinary writing. Because of all the contents in it, there are many meanings, messages, also very good meanings. The analysis of one of the meanings of the name, as well as the expressions used, shows that we must believe in a good future and believe in what God has planned and what our parents have given us is the most beautiful and best thing.

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

Yes it is, there some data can be used as data to answer.

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

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Yes it is, data have information which is scientific methods, qualitative observation with the background of the problem. Qualitative studies are based on efforts to build perspectives that are studied in detail and are composed of words and are complex

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Yes it does, because this paper has been identified by previous research and the data has been published in the original source, which is a novel with the theme NKCTHI

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

No it doesn't, because this theoretical just only explain the meaning of the word go home and the name of the cloud that makes it clear to the readers

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

Maybe yes it does, because problems that the meaning of the go home alone is to invite those of us who are far from home to remember going home

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

Yes it does, because the problems that come from the meaning of the word go home and the name of the cloud are common among teenagers.

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

Yes, The problem is raised from the author's interest and ability to discuss the problems that occur

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

Starting from the story of a mother named Awan, she told her daughter, "Ibu mencoba menjadi 'awan' yang diinginkan nenek mu selama 27 tahun, tetapi itu tidak mudah. Tugasnya berat, menyalurkan hujan agar isi bumi tidak mengalami kekeringan juga menghalangi matahari agar bumi tidak kepanasan. Padahal ibu hanya ingin seperti 'bohlam' yang hanya mampu menerangi ruangan kecil dan menghangatkan seisi ruang. Karena itu Sudah lebih dari cukup". Sometimes the meaning of a name becomes an obstacle for the owner to name it.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

The analysis of one of the meanings of the name, as well as the expressions used, shows that we must believe in a good future and believe in what God has planned and what our parents have given us is the most beautiful and best thing.

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